

THEOLOGICAL AND ANTHROPOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN RELIGIOUS STUDIES

Media Zainul Bahri

*Faculty of Theology, Syarif Hidayatullah State Islamic University (UIN) of Jakarta***Abstract**

This article discusses two important approaches in religious studies: theological and anthropological. The theological approach is a way of understanding religion by reading religious texts such as the scriptures or other sacred religious texts, while the anthropological approach is understanding the relationship between religion and human culture. In fact, theological approach cannot be separated from the anthropological because theological understanding emerges in the historical and cultural context in which world religions emerge. This article is an analytical descriptive study.

Keywords: Religious studies, Theological and Antropological Approaches, E.B. Taylor, Clifford Geertz

Introduction

Since long time ago, many people have considered religious studies or scientific studies of religion as something absurd and unpleasant. According to Ninian Smart (1927-2001), professor of religious studies over more than four decades, and a powerful advocate of the study of religion for the enrichment of common humanity, it is called absurd because scientific approaches tend to distort inner feelings and responses to the transcendent/divine. It is called disliked because scientific study brings a (cold) rational approach to what should be “warm and thrilling.” This assumption is wrong, although it is completely understandable. Of course the humanities—including religious studies—must deal with inner feelings, because humans cannot be understood if their emotions and religious experiences are not understood.. This is definitely different from the approach in the natural sciences which treats ‘rocks’ or ‘electrons’ as inanimate objects [1]. Religious studies are also disliked due to the problem of the strengthening of religious fundamentalism today which is “allergic” to scientific religious studies, because it is considered ‘to endanger’ faith, ‘mislead’ or at least make a religious person away from his/her religion because it examines existing religious beliefs with certainly scientific methods that regard religion as part of culture so that it is legitimate to be ‘criticized’ explicitly.

What is Religious Studies?

According to Smart, first of all it must be distinguished between “doing theology” and “studying religion”. To do theology, in a general understanding, is to articulate a belief. Processing and making arguments and looking for justifications—although from scientific materials—but in order to strengthen their religious beliefs. Included in doing theology is writing works with the purpose of preaching, showing the weaknesses of other people’s beliefs—and at the same time-- showing the perfection of one’s own religion. However for Smart, in the study of religion itself, theology is part of the phenomenon that must be understood. For example, the architectural writings of Le Corbusier, a French architect, of course, must be included as material in compiling the history of modern architecture, even though Corbusier’s own writings aim to be practical and are part of his activities as an architect. Architectural historians need not be architects. In the same way, a scholar

of the scientific study of religion can benefit from theological works without necessarily being a theologian.

Studying religion scientifically means explaining religious phenomena practiced by its adherents, whether observed from the aspects of their religious experience, social relations, cultural, economic and political behavior related to their religious activities, with a certain set of scientific approaches or methods. According to Smart, the scientific study of religion is aspectual, polymethodical, pluralistic, and without clear boundaries. *Firstly*, It is aspectual in the sense that religion must be treated as an aspect of existence. People behave or react religiously, this is what is raised by religious studies; as economics elevates human economic behavior. *Secondly*, The study of religion is polymethodical in the sense that different methods or disciplines are used to discuss these aspects. Therefore, a scholar of religion needs to understand religion with historical, philosophical, theological, sociological, psychological, phenomenological and other approaches. *Third*, It is pluralistic in nature because there are many religions and religious traditions, and it would appear that religious studies that are carried out seriously will be definitely attracted to more than one religious tradition. *Fourth*, The study of religion is without clear boundaries, because it is impossible or unrealistic to generalize a standard definition of religion. One definition (of religion) may describe some special elements of one or two religions, but may not include many other religions [2].

Religion as part of culture is a religion that being understood, lived and practiced by historical humans and because of that it becomes part of the object of scientific study. Included in this are products produced by religious actors such as religious texts or religious institutions and others. All products of religious thought and activity are usually closely related to political, economic, cultural and social activities which further strengthen religion as an object of scientific study.

The theological approach is a way of understanding religion by reading religious texts such as the scriptures, sayings of the prophets and writings of religious scholars and saints in religious traditions. The theological approach is a very common way of understanding religion in world religions. However, it turns out that religious sacred texts were born and developed according to the culture in which these religions arose. The

holy book (scripture), for example, was born in a certain historical and cultural context. Likewise, the sayings of the prophets which later became religious laws also appeared in a particular culture. Therefore, to understand Islam one must understand Arabic culture. Likewise for Hinduism one must understand Indian culture, for Confucianism and Taoism one must understand Chinese culture, for Judaism one must understand culture in the Middle East, and so on. Professor Hassan Hanafi, a leading Egyptian Muslim intellectual, states that God's revelation came down in a dynamic historical-anthropological context, not static [3]. The Shari'a of the prophets will vary according to their respective cultural contexts which are indeed unique and particular. In the language of Professor Shahab Ahmed (2016), religion and religious teachings cannot be separated from Pre-Text, Text, and Con-Text [4]. Therefore, theological and anthropological approaches are two ideal approaches to understand religion and become interesting approaches in religious studies.

Theological Approach

This approach in a fairly long historical period is the most dominant and most influential approach in religious studies or the comparative study of religions, even to this day, although it no longer dominates. For centuries, theology was considered as the "Queen of the Sciences", especially in the Jewish, Christian and Islamic world. This is a normative and subjective approach. With this approach, a follower of a religion, whether Christianity, Islam or another religion, when making a theological study, usually does one of two things: *first*, internal study. In this case, a religious scholar/researcher is an insider who tries actively in his scientific activities to preserve and promote the superiority of his religion and defend it from threats or attacks from other people. *Second*, external. In this case, a researcher or adherent of a certain religion conducts a study of other people's religions/beliefs to 'assess' and 'judge' them by the measure of the researcher's religion (or prescriptive attitude). In the past, this approach was also called the textual approach or the biblical approach with its main characteristics: apologist and polemist.

In Christian history, for example, great theologians like St. Augustine of Hippo with his works of *On Christian Doctrine and Confessions*, Thomas Aquinas with *Summa Theologica*, Paul Tillich with *Systematic Theology*, Karl Barth with his *magnum oppus Church Dogmatics*, and many others, use a single theological approach. They do not only make theological works that campaign and deepen the superiority of Christian teachings, but also evaluate other religions. Thomas Aquinas for example taught that all religions outside of Christianity are false. We can read volumes of Christian theologians from the Middle Ages to the modern with an apologetic theological model.

Islamic studies in the middle age did the same way. We can read pre and medieval theological works such as al-Ghazali with one of his works, *al-Qawl al-Jamīl Fi Radd 'alā Man Ghayyara al-Injīl*, Ibn 'Arabi with *al-Futūhāt al-Makkiyyah*, Ali Ibn Hazm through *al-Faṣl Fi al-Milal wa al-Ahwā wa al-Niḥal*, Abdul Karim Shahrastani through *al-Milal wa al-Niḥal*, Ibn Taymiyyah through *al-Jawāb al-Sahīh Liman Baddala Dīn*

al-Masīh, and Abdul Qahir Ibn Tahir Ibn Muhammad al-Baghdadi through *al-Farqu Bayn al-Firaq*. These works also not only declare the perfection of Islam but also strip away the flaws of other religions. In modern times such works have appeared more and more.

Theology vis-a-vis Religious Studies

As already mentioned, the task of a theologian is to promote the superiority of his religious tradition and convince people that the doctrines and teachings of this religion can give meaning and hope in an uncertain life. But more than that, a theologian can also discuss important contextual issues such as the environment, global climate change, human rights, problems of intolerance, marginalized groups of people and others. All of these issues are given a theological value. To what extent theological doctrines can respond to these important issues. However, a theologian is still an 'insider' who interpreting his theological views.

The discipline of religious studies or comparative study of religions is different from the theological tasks above, at least that's what happened in universities in the West that have departments of religious studies. Scholars of religious studies must be designed not to be 'insiders' in any religious tradition. His task is to carry out scientific studies of religious traditions with certain scientific approaches, whether with phenomenological, historical, sociological, anthropological, hermeneutic or other approaches. Thus, a scholar is not an 'insider' playing the role of a theologian addressing a particular religious audience. Even though a scholar of religious studies is a religious person or has adherence to a particular religion, he must avoid the 'normative role' of a theologian. He must avoid judging, determining, and promoting the values, norms and claims of the religious traditions he studies [5]. His task is to classify and analyze the claims and contexts around that tradition, whether it is history, culture, or social interactions that give rise to the theological views and claims.

Indeed, here it must be understood the fundamental difference between religion, the study of religion, and being religious [6]. Many scholars, students, and especially non-graduate people are confused to distinguish these three points. In Indonesia, almost all religious scholars who carry out scientific studies on religion—even become professors in (certain) religious studies, but at the same time often become theologians in the midst of their society or community. When speaking in public as well, he 'unifies' the attitude between being a scholar who tries to explain his scientific analysis while also making values, defining, and promoting his religious tradition. This attitude is similar to that of Christian theologians in the West, also in Asia in the 1950s to 1990s. However, in the West, there is gradually a clear distinction between theological figures and scholars of religious studies by looking at their actions and works..

To be a scholar of religion who is proficient in religion does not have to be a theologian (insider), just as someone who is religious does not mean that he cannot become an expert in scientific studies of religion. This is in accordance with the adage that "to be good at teaching biology you don't have to be a frog or a fish

first". Currently, when the study of religion or Comparative Religion is approached with a multi-disciplinary scientific method, the lecturer of religious studies does not have to be someone who is trained in that discipline. Sociologists, anthropologists, political scientists, psychologists, philosophers, and cultural scientists can teach religious studies or Comparative Religion with their scientific approach or perspectives. Indeed, religion is the main object for religious studies, but its studies are no longer dominated by only scholars in religious studies or theologian [7].

Anthropological Approach

This approach seeks to understand human-made cultures related to religion. The extent to which religion influences culture and vice versa, the extent to which the culture of a group of people influences religious interpretations. In the history of religious studies there are several figures who have always been the reference for this approach, which became widely known as the study of Religious Anthropology. For example Edward Burnett Taylor (1832-1917), James George Frazer (1854-1941), Andrew Lang (1844-1912), Wilhelm Schmidt (1868-1954), Clifford Geertz (1926-2006) and others. We will focus on just two figures, Taylor and Clifford Geertz, whose thoughts were discussed in the department of religious studies.

Edward Burnett Taylor (1832-1917)

Edward Tylor is a scientist (an anthropologist) who most of his life is used to direct attention to primitive people, especially to the Indian tribes in Central America. For his very serious observations, he produced quality works such as *Anahuac: Or Mexico and The Mexican Ancient and Modern* (1861) and *The Early History of Mankind and the Development of Civilization* (1865). However, his peak work, *Primitive Culture* (1871), which he wrote in two large volumes, has led him to become a renowned British anthropologist. *Primitive Culture* can be called a 'bible' for later scientists who were deeply inspired by what they called "Mr. Taylor's Science" [8].

At first, Tylor was not interested in religious matters. However, his involvement in the life of primitive people requires him to understand their beliefs about spirits, gods, myths, and the origins of those beliefs. After a long struggle with primitive culture, Tylor came to the conclusion that religion is "belief in something spiritual". According to him, all religions, big and small, primitive and modern, have always based their belief in spirits who think, behave and feel like humans. Therefore, the essence of every religion is *animism* (*anima*: spirit), namely belief in a living being, who has power, who is behind everything. This animism that becomes the focus of Tylor's attention.

In primitive society, initially two questions and concerns arose: *first*, what is the difference between a living and a dead body; what causes humans to wake up, sleep, faint, get sick and die? *Second*, what form appears in human dreams and fantasies? Observing these two problems, "*the ancient savage philosophers*" of primitive society then tried to answer them in two stages: *first*, by stating that every human being has two things, namely the soul and spirit (*phantom*) as a shadow of the second self for soul. These two things are

also considered as an inseparable part of the body. *Second*, by combining the soul and spirit earlier, the 'wild philosophers' succeeded in discovering the conception of a Soul that Has a Personality [9]. Their vivid experiences of death and dreams allowed primitive peoples to think for the first time of the simple theory that all life is caused by a spirit or spiritual principle. They regard the spirit as a very ethereal, insubstantial shadow of a human being with a very subtle, thin and shadow form. He is the one who gives life to humans [10].

Furthermore, according to Tylor, animism has developed. Initially, people only thought of an individual spirit as something small and specific, merged with the trees, rivers or animals they encountered. Then, this spirit power started to grow. In the minds of primitive peoples, the spirit of a single tree gradually developed into the spirit of the forest or the spirit of the whole tree. Furthermore, the same spirit will also be considered increasingly separated from the object that first mastered by further strengthening its own identity and character. Each place and region has spirits of different strengths and levels: the highest spirit, the high spirit, the low spirit, and the lowest spirit. There are spirits of wind, rain and sun which are higher in rank than the spirits of trees and rivers. The tree spirits can't do anything about it if the sun spirit decides not to rain so the trees dry up or the Rain Goddess decides to destroy the trees by sending a flood [11]. With a theological view of the various levels of spirits and their powers, the worship of many spirits (*polytheism*) arose.

Such a complex polytheistic system was characteristic of the religious model of the most ancient times. No matter how simple, this civilization will always seek the highest level, namely when they try to form a society that has one God, a single power that overcomes other gods. According to Tylor, slowly but surely, every civilization will lead to a new direction, the final stage of animism, namely belief in one God (*monotheism*), although the paths taken are not always the same. And without any doubt, the Christian and Jewish societies (including Islam, sic.) are the best examples of this last stage. They have formed a very logical final formula of the entire developmental process that had begun centuries before, shrouded in the dark fog of pre-historic times. That is, when the first human whom Tylor called a 'wild philosopher' concluded that spirits controlled the world around him [12].

With the various explanations above, Tylor wants to show that the origins of religious belief (God) in mankind actually evolved: from animism to polytheism and ended in monotheism. Tylor, who was born and raised in England, was certainly influenced by Charles Darwin's theory of evolution. Darwin, who published *The Origin of Species* (1859), later became a byword and a highly controversial figure, especially in England. According to Daniel L. Pals, his *idea of development* took its most obvious form in Tylor's thought. In the following years, as the debate intensified, many thinkers emerged who raised troubling questions about basic elements of Christian beliefs such as the historical truths of the Bible, the truth of miracles and the question of the divinity of Jesus Christ. With the publication of *Primitive Culture* which brought a new theory about

the origins of all religions, including Christianity, the doubts that had previously settled in European society grew stronger [13]. Tylor's research results actually show conclusions similar to those of sociologists like Durkheim, for example, that religion is actually the result of social (and cultural) construction of humans, and not revelations handed down by God as believed by believers.

Tylor's theory was then met with resistance, especially from the church scholars. Andrew Lang for example, a folklorist from Scotland, who had previously been a follower of Tylor's theory, later refuted it. Based on the research he did, there is evidence that primitive society from the beginning has had embraced monotheism. Primitive religious understanding, says Lang, never began with polytheism and their original monotheism was not a complete development of animism. Lang's observations later received support from Wilhelm Schmidt, an anthropologist and Catholic priest from Germany. He also argued that the religious understanding of all primitive societies was monotheistic from the start, and monotheism was the original form of all human religions that have existed, until the present day [14].

In religious studies, the question arises: in studying religion, why does it always have to start with "where did religion originate?" To this question there are two possible answers. *First*, it is a "general symptom" in the Humanities discipline. If we study philosophy as a discipline, for example, we usually study the history of philosophy *first*: where and when did philosophy begin, who were the first philosophical figures, what model of philosophy first emerged, and so on. *Second*, in the Study of Religion, especially in the context of the figure of Max Müller, a British scholar with German nationality who is a philologist of Indian religions, tracing the origins of religion means an attempt to find the most original and earliest form of religion because it is considered the purest form. It is a challenging endeavor to find the purest form of religion because it will reveal a great mystery and become a basis for analyzing the historical development of religions.

Third, in religious studies, the issue of where religion originates is the most crucial problem, especially in the Western Christian world. Before the emergence of descriptive or scientific studies of religion, religious knowledge in the West was completely dominated by Theology (Theology as the "*Queen of Sciences*" also has actually become a common phenomenon in the Islamic world (East) for quite a long period of time). Therefore, in the context of Western Christianity (Europe), when anthropological, sociological, and psychological theories emerge that reject God, the question of the origin of religion is 'a life-and-death' problem that cannot be negotiated anymore, because it concerns the main things and the main thing in religion, namely the belief in the existence of God. The church, with various propaganda and proselytizing, wants to stem the understanding and movement of atheism and draw European society back into the arms of the church.

If scholars agree that the theory of the origins of religion is still important for students and academics to debate as initial knowledge, then this must be done in a

scientific matter and not with the aim of preaching, namely wanting to show the superiority of religious arguments *vis-a-vis* anthropological, sociological and psychological studies that have been produced through a long series of research. What often happens is that students and academics do not properly understand the theories of the origins of religion through the first writings of the initiating scholars. What often happens, they discuss the theories through third or fourth references or through translation books, which are very likely to have reduced the main material of the theories.

In an interesting article entitled *The study of religion and the rise of atheism: conflict or confirmation?* (2011) Michael Buckley, professor of Theology at the Department of Religious Studies at the University of Santa Clara, California, explained that there was indeed a fierce battle between *Uratheismus* supporters and *Urmonotheismus* ones. The scientific quest of 19th century anthropologists, sociologists and psychologists for the culture of primitive peoples required them to seek deeper into the origins of primitive religious beliefs in the Ultimate Reality. And the results of that research then became something very bitter for the church. E.B. Taylor, for example, concluded that his scientific research had strengthened his personal position to be an agnostic who was skeptical of religious faith [15]. Sir John Lubbock through *The Origin of Civilization and the First Condition of Man* (1870) as quoted by Buckley, put forward the thesis that atheism is indeed the earliest and most primitive phenomenon of human religion. This phenomenon, before the time of Lubbock, has given fresh blood to the theory of August Comte (1798-1857) about the three stages of the intellectual development of society. Through in-depth research on religious culture in primitive societies, Lubbock finds that "*Uratheismus not in an explicit denial of the reality of any god, but in the absence within these earliest cultures of all religion*" [16].

In line with Lubbock, other scholars such as Durkheim, George Frazer, and Sigmund Freud both asserted that totem worship, as the highest representation of reality, in primitive societies was the most primordial form of belief, and the most original foundation of all religions. In looking at the religious experience in humans, Freud dived into the deepest psychic experiences of humans through what he called "longing for Oedipus" and his feelings of guilt for killing his father. Through psychoanalysis, Freud argued that basically what is called God does not actually exist, he is only an image (picture) of a great father. Therefore, if the totem is the earliest form of surrogate father, then the concept of a god or gods appears later [17].

In the same spirit as Freud, Carl Gustav Jung (died 1961), a psychologist who is also against religion, argues that what is called God is actually a representation of a number of libido energies. Through a series of psychological research, Jung believed that God is a construct of the libido that is based on the image of a mother rather than a father figure (In terms of this figure, Jung is different from Freud who refers more to the father figure) [18]. The figures above have come to the conclusion that religion can be found in the earliest

primitive humans, but not with the concept of god. Tylor, for example, although he defined religion as “belief in spiritual beings”, in the view of ancient society, these so-called spiritual beings were none other than individual spirits residing in nature, not God from “another realm”.

Contrary to the views of the above scholars, the supporters of *Urmonotheism* also point to scientific arguments for belief in God in the most ancient primitive societies. Wilhelm Schmidt, for example, by adopting Andrew Lang’s theory of high gods, asserts through his work *Der Ursprung der Gottesidee* as quoted by Buckley, that the idea of the Supreme Being can be found in almost all cultures of primitive societies. Expressed in the same form and model, but the idea of it is prominent enough to make its position quite dominant and unquestionable. Because of this, the ideas and beliefs about *Urmonotheismus* existed in its earliest stages as the religious object of all subsequent primitive cultural models. Primitive society had no difficulty recognizing the idea of a Supreme Being. Thus, monotheism is at an early stage, not a late one, in the development of the religious thought of mankind. More than that, Raffaele Pettazzoni, according to Buckley, shows that the idea of primitive monotheism is a form of revolution against polytheism in primitive society itself. Pettazzoni conducted research on primitive Maori society. They worshiped *Io* as the god of the sky. They also believe that *Io* is the creator of other gods like *Rangi* and *Papa*. However, in the final analysis, Pettazzoni discovers that *Io* is *Rangi* himself and it is *Rangi* who stands behind *Io* as the real God of Heaven who ultimately exalts his position as *Io* (under the name *Io*), an uncreated substance and as the initial source of everything [19]. Thus, Pettazzoni’s research concluded that from the beginning the beliefs of primitive peoples were not merely monotheism, but also that they opposed polytheism by demonstrating the only Supreme Power as the initial source and creator of all things, including creating minor gods.

In the heated debate between proponents of *Uratheismus* and *Urmonotheismus*, on the academic front, the research that has been carried out by Lubbock, Taylor, Evans-Pritchard, Frazer, and Durkheim for example, or evolutionists such as Darwin and Robert N. Bellah, who most recently, has very strong influence, and become a mandatory reference for the reviewers. More than that, it has also become a popular general reading. On a broad scale, their works together with Darwin’s theory of evolution led to the strengthening of skeptical, even atheistic views and attitudes in European society in the 19th century. Of course, such anthropological, sociological, and psychological research that underlying on observation is difficult to disprove, although there is always the possibility of being broken with different evidence and new discoveries. During the golden age of the scholars, even to this day, the church (theologians) or scientists who agree with the church always show confrontation.

This attitude of confrontation, even hostility, was regretted by Buckley. In the context of the dominance of theories of the origins of religion which ignore the

revelation of God, Buckley proposes the scientific discipline of Religious Studies to explore theological endeavors that differ in its nuance from what was carried out by Theological Studies in the 19th and 20th centuries. In other words, it is no longer time for theologians and theological disciplines to continue to be hostile to scientists. If the study of theology focuses on the sciences of divinity, then the theologians must undertake a journey towards in-depth knowledge of anything about God that will produce a positive and enlightening perspective. Buckley wrote:

There is no time now to argue and nuance this suggestion with the distinctions it obviously cries for, but only to propose that the scientific study of religion could well call the theological enterprise to an inquiry quite different from that which obtained in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries. For, to allow the final word to Nicholas Lash: “Every Christian, and hence every Christian theologian, is called to journey in the direction of deeper knowledge of the things of God, and the journey is a homecoming, for God is our end as well as our beginning.” [20]

If human culture has been explored in such a way by scientists in various scientific disciplines, then interest matters to researchers of scientific studies of religion, according to Buckley, is to reveal things related to God. For example, revealing important moments of human spiritual experience about God. Buckley rhetorically asks: can Christ be seen as giving light, so that it is interesting to study, rather than having to compete with controversial problems that have been found in scientific studies of religion? Christian theologians may be able to study well about the illumination of Jesus without having to look for data on human culture, but they can sufficiently show what can be learned from God. *Nostra aetate* produced by the Second Vatican Council is a reflection of the spiritual wealth of the Holy Father. The *Nostra*, according to Buckley, has acknowledged that God’s Light can illuminate anyone of His creatures and in any religious tradition. Can Christian theologians make a scientific study of the inner wealth of Christian figures about God to produce such amazing *Nostra*? [21]

Clifford Geertz (1926-2006)

Another anthropologist who deserves to be our example is Clifford Geertz. Geertz, one of the most well-known American anthropology masters and made famous in a small town in East Jawa-Indonesia, because of his research which was highly reckoned with in the 1970s due to the new concept he initiated, namely interpretive anthropology. Geertz’s career began when he was a doctoral student in his second year at Harvard, Geertz and his wife left for the island of Java and settled for two years in Mojokuto (Kediri) East Java, to study a heterogeneous society in terms of culture and religious beliefs. After receiving his doctorate in anthropology in 1956, he accompanied his wife again and came to Indonesia, specifically to the island of Bali for an anthropological research. Geertz’s main mission as an anthropologist in Java and Bali is ethnography, which is to provide a detailed and systematic description of the people on the two islands in order to reveal

how the various aspects of people's lives can merge into an intact culture [22].

In 1960 Geertz published *The Religion of Java*, a very famous and controversial work on the *abangan-santri-priyayi* trichotomy in the pattern of socio-religious relations in Javanese society. It is this work that is always remembered by the anthropological community around the world and brought Geertz to the stage of fame and a special place in the world of American anthropology. After that, other quality works were also appeared, *Agricultural Revolution* (1963), *The Socio-History of an Indonesian Town* (1965), *Islam Observed* (1968), *The Interpretation of Culture* (1973), *Meaning and Order in Moroccan* (1980) and *Local Knowledge* (1983).

In an essay entitled *Thick Description: Toward an Interpretative Theory of Culture*, which is found in *The Interpretation of Culture*, Geertz reminded, as quoted by L. Pals, that although the culture word is understood by anthropologists with different meanings, but the key to understand is the idea of meaning (meaning or significance). Humans, said Geertz by quoting Weber, are “animals confined in webs of meaning (*significance*) that they spun themselves”. Therefore, if someone wants to do what anthropologists have done, namely to explain other people's cultures, then he has no other choice but to use the method that the British philosopher, Gilbert Ryle, called “Thick Description” (in-depth painting). One must be able to describe not only what actually happened, but also (explain) how one's understanding of that incident [23].

Ryle gave the example of two kids winking. The first child blinks his eyes without realizing it (accidentally) because of the motion of his eye nerves, while the other child blinks his eyes at someone else on purpose. Physically or “*thin description*” (a shallow painting) shows that the two events are the same. However, if one explores further the significance of each event, one will find a difference. The first incident is meaningless. On the other hand, the second blink is full of meaning that the second child wants to convey. “*Thick description*” which involves the meaning of the event shows that the wink of the second child (wink) is much different from the blink of the first child (twitch). Therefore, according to Geertz, it can be understood that ethnography—as well as anthropology—in general always involves “deep painting”. His task is not merely to describe the structure of primitive tribes or parts of rituals that are more specific to religious people, for example the Muslim fasting practice in the month of Ramadan. Its main task is to search for meaning, find the essence behind one's actions, the meaning that lies behind all life and ritual thoughts, structures and beliefs of the studied objects [24].

However, it must also be remembered that a culture is not just a matter of meaning, or only as something that is purely filled with symbol systems like mathematics. Customs or people's behavior must also be observed because culture finds its articulation through behavior, or more precisely through social action [25]. If interpretive anthropology is a way to see the system of meaning and values that people use in

carrying out their lives, then this interpretive anthropology will always be interested in religious issues. Geertz was very sure of that and he showed it in his very famous book, *The Religion of Jawa* (1960). Anthropologists call this work as the best ethnographic book in the American anthropological tradition. Geertz not only conducts in-depth studies by being directly involved with the life and language of the Javanese people, but he also discusses in detail the complex relationships between Islamic, Hindu and local indigenous beliefs (*Abangan, Kejawen*: Javanese religion). In this book, Geertz sees religion not merely as an expression of social and economic needs but also as a cultural fact as it is in the culture of the Javanese people [26].

In his research on the unique culture and religion of the Balinese people, Geertz made a conclusion that any study of religion will be successful if it takes two important steps: *first*, one must start by analyzing the set of meanings contained in the religious symbols themselves. According to Geertz, this is quite a difficult task. *Second*, what is no less difficult, namely because these symbols are closely related to the structure of society and the psychological aspects of members of the community, the series of symbols must be continuously traced, whether from the way of creating, the process of receiving and interpreting them and deviations of those meanings. This relationship can be analogous to an image with three points forming a triangle. The first point is for symbols, the second point is for society, and the third point is for individual psychology [27].

Another example of the use of interpretive anthropology is Geertz's work entitled *Islam Observed* (1968). This book describes a comparison of Indonesian and Moroccan Islamic culture. Besides these two countries have population majority of Muslim, both have also experienced drastic social changes in the modern era. Most Indonesians work in agriculture (please note that Geertz's research was conducted in the 1960s) and the majority of Moroccans work as herders. Both of them had been colonized by Western nations (Indonesia by the Dutch and Morocco by the French). Geertz wanted to see the important role religion has played and is currently playing in the process of social transformation that has taken place in both countries [28].

In the process of the entry of Islam into Indonesia, in this case Java, Geertz created a description of the legend of Sunan Kalijaga as a *Wali* (saint) who was very popular in spreading Islam in Java. He was born into the ruling family of the time, during the Hindu-Buddhist era, when the high-caste ruling class was considered the country's spiritual elite. In an atmosphere of palace aristocratic life, the implementation of religious rites actually functioned as political power and religious authority for the king at the same time. The interesting thing about the legend of Kalijaga is that when he became the guardian of the propagator of Islam, who was ordained by Sunan Ampel, he did not leave his childhood Hindu-Buddhist culture. According to Geertz, he then helped establish the Mataram kingdom and took advantage of his position in royal ceremonies to introduce Islam, and one of the ways was to continue to voice the values of Hinduism and Buddhism [29].

Synonymous with the story of Sunan Kalijaga, according to Geertz, the emergence of Islam in Morocco can be seen well from the life story of a saint named Sidi Lahsen Lyusi (real name is Abu Ali al-Hasan Ibn Mas'ud al-Yusi), one of the last generation of Maraboutism who lived around the 1600's. Maraboutism is a mystical understanding and practice of Moroccan Islam inherited from the Murabithun dynasty. Like Kalijaga, Lyusi is considered by Moroccan Muslims as a Wali (saint) who is knowledgeable, has noble character and has spiritual charisma so that he also has many supernatural powers [30]. According to Geertz, Kalijaga and Lyusi have a lot in common. Both emerged and played a role in critical times in the development of their society, but then they found a way out and a solution. They are both wandered from place to place eagerly searching. They are both lived in proximity: Kalijaga in the sixteenth century and Lyusi in the seventeenth century. Both of them also come from the elite of their society, Kalijaga is an aristocrat, and Lyusi is a sharif (descendant of the Prophet Muhammad) [31].

However, continued Geertz, there are significant differences between both of them in their socio-cultural context and problem solving. In Java, the crisis facing Kalijaga was the result of the weakening of the Hindu-Buddhist Majapahit and its demoralization, followed by the introduction of vital and dynamic Islam. Meanwhile in Morocco, the crisis that Lyusi finds is a society has devoted Islamic for centuries but has experienced disintegration from within, which makes society split into small groups. They need the guardian as the central figure. Therefore, if Kalijaga is looking for a solution to the crisis of his society by finding harmony and aesthetic integrity, then Lyusi is trying to overcome it by directing society to strict moral requirements (by implementing *Shariah* and morals) which are believed to be true religious teachings [32]. In Geertz's definition, the religions in Morocco and Indonesia, although both are Islamic, show very different cultures, feelings and motivations. In Indonesia (meaning Java, sic.), there is calm, patience, introspection, full of consideration, sensitivity, asceticism and even it might say almost no obsession. In Morocco, Islam is active, aggressive, passionate, courageous, tenacious, moralist, populist and obsessive [33].

Conclusion

Religion as a scientific object requires it to comply to scientific methods. Theological and anthropological approaches are two scientific methods in understanding religion critically. These two approaches cannot be separated because many normative theological aspects are closely related to anthropological facts. Anthropological studies of religion such as those carried out by Clifford Geertz show that the face of religion is very plural because it is practiced in various human cultures. In Indonesia in 1970s, for example, there is a religious model that is calm, patience, introspection, full of consideration, sensitivity, asceticism and even it might say almost no obsession. In Morocco in 1970s, Islam is active, aggressive, passionate, courageous, tenacious, moralist, populist and obsessive. However, even though in religious studies, religion is treated as empir-

ical data (to be cold and rational), for adherents of religion (believers) it remains as something "warm and thrilling".

References

1. Ninian Smart, "Batas-Batas Studi Agama Ilmiah," in Ahmad Norma Permata, ed., *Metodologi Studi Agama* (Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar, 2000), p. 143.
2. Ninian Smart, "Batas-Batas," p. 148.
3. Hassan Hanafi, *Dirasat Islamiyyat* (Egypt: Maktabah al-Anjelu al-Mishriyyah, n.y), p. 71.
4. Shahab Ahmed, *What is Islam? The Importance of Being Islamic* (Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 2016).
5. Hillary Rodrigues and John S. Harding, *Introduction to The Study Of Religion* (London and New York: Routledge, 2009), pp. 44-45.
6. Rodrigues, *Introduction*, p. 45.
7. Rodrigues, *Introduction*, p. 45.
8. Daniel L. Pals, *Eight Theories of Religion* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2006), Edisi ke-2, p. 19.
9. L. Pals, *Eight Theories*, pp. 26-27.
10. L. Pals, *Eight Theories*, p. 27.
11. L. Pals, *Eight Theories*, p. 28-29.
12. L. Pals, *Eight Theories*, p. 29.
13. L. Pals, *Eight Theories*, p. 20.
14. Rodrigues, *Introduction*, p. 53.
15. L. Pals, *Eight Theories*, p. 10. See Michael J. Buckley S.J., "The study of religion and the rise of atheism: conflict or confirmation?," in David F. Ford, ed., *Fields Of faith, Theology and Religious Studies for the Twenty-first Century* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2011), p. 13.
16. Buckley, "The study of religion and the rise of atheism," p. 13.
17. Buckley, "The study of religion and the rise of atheism," p. 13.
18. Buckley, "The study of religion and the rise of atheism," pp. 13-14.
19. Buckley, "The study of religion and the rise of atheism," p. 16.
20. Buckley, "The study of religion and the rise of atheism," p. 24.
21. Buckley, "The study of religion and the rise of atheism," p. 23.
22. L. Pals, *Eight Theories*, pp. 261-262.
23. L. Pals, *Eight Theories*, p. 267.
24. L. Pals, *Eight Theories*, p. 267.
25. L. Pals, *Eight Theories*, p. 268.
26. L. Pals, *Eight Theories*, p. 269.
27. L. Pals, *Eight Theories*, pp. 272-273.
28. Clifford Geertz, *Islam Observed: Religious Development in Morocco and Indonesia* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1975), p. 4, pp. 13-14.
29. Geertz, *Islam Observed*, pp. 25-27.
30. L. Pals, *Eight Theories*, p. 278.
31. Geertz, *Islam Observed*, pp. 29-30.
32. Geertz, *Islam Observed*, pp. 30-31, pp. 35-37.
33. Geertz, *Islam Observed*, p. 16.